

DETERMINING LECTURERS' TEST SCORING KNOWLEDGE BY LEVEL OF WORKING EXPERIENCE: A CASE STUDY OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN ZAMFARA STATE.

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Abstract

This paper assessed test scoring knowledge of tertiary institution lecturers in Zamfara State. It determined the proportion of low experience, quite experience, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low scoring knowledge. It also finds out whether significant differences exist in lecturers' test scoring knowledge and level of working experience. The paper answered one research question and tested one hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Population of this study consists of 300 lecturers in Zamfara State that were sampled through multi stage cluster sampling. The survey design was employed for the study. Teachers Test Scoring Scale (TTSS) was adopted as instrument of data collection. Similarly, out of 300 instruments administered to lecturers, only 289 were retrieved, yielding 96.3% response rate. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used for the analysis of data. The result of the study revealed that tertiary institution lecturers in Zamfara State are knowledgeable of test scoring and that their scoring knowledge does not differ significantly by level of working experience. The study recommended in-service training, workshop, monitoring of assessment from test construction, administration of test scoring. It also recommended creation of assessment policy such as preparing marking scheme in tertiary institution.

Keywords: Test scoring knowledge, lecturers' level of working experience.

Introduction

Tertiary institutions were established for the purpose of post secondary school teaching and learning. In order to ascertain whether or not learning has taken place, lecturers try to evaluate students. This process of evaluating learners is commonly known as assessment. It is the process by which lecturers collect data about overall learning progress for students' promotion, placement and graduation. Evaluating students' learning progress and achievement is determined using scores obtained from instrument known as test. The Federal Republic of Nigeria, (FRN, 2004), recognized the importance of test in certification of tertiary institution

students when it stated succinctly that; certification of tertiary institution students shall be based on overall test scores obtained by them from series of continuous measurement and judgment in form of end-of-semester examination. Test scoring is therefore an essential component of assessment that is gaining increasing attention in education in recent years. Educational researchers now recognized that test scoring knowledge act as instrument through which both lecturers and students can benefit enormously. Sidhu, (2005), states that “scoring is a relative judgment of student’s item response”. It is an aspect of testing that has to do with making judgment about response to test items and assigning numerical values to the responses. In particular, Sidhu, (2005), points out that the functions of test scores are to provide feedback to lecturers and students regarding the extent to which instructional objectives are achieved, account to parents on the achievement and progress of their children, help in identifying students' academic strengths and weaknesses and determine students’ promotion, placement and graduation. The role of scores is very important as tertiary institutions rely on them to account for students’ learning outcome. Test scores do not only provide the extent of mental ability of learners in tertiary institutions, rather they provide the extent of other aspects of human behaviour such as interest and attitude. From this point of view, lecturers' knowledge of other aspects of human behaviour places them in a strong position to utilize such information for educational and vocational purposes. Lecturers function not only as instructors but counselors and psychologists, using test scores, they assist students whose performances are affected by attitude and interest with counseling advice like inter faculty, change of course, deferring program or even withdrawal. Hence, test scores have become an important aspect of our educational culture that both lecturers and students not only attach great importance to scores but are also interested in how the scores were conducted as well as the relationship between the scores and grades that are awarded. Meanwhile, according to Osuji, Okonkwo, & Nnachi, (2006), there are different tests scoring techniques, and the use of a particular technique is determined by examinee freedom of expression.

Multiple choice tests are scored via the following ways:

- i. Strip key: in this method answers to tests items are scored by direct comparison of the examinees answer with the marking keys.
- ii. Scoring stencils: this is prepared by pending holes on blank answer sheet where the correct answers are supposed to appear. Scoring is then done by laying the stencils over each sheet and numbers of answers checked through the holes are counted.
- iii. Machine Scoring: this involves scoring students' responses with the computer and other possible scoring devices using certified answer keys prepared for the test items.

Essay tests on their part are scored through the following ways:

- i. Analytical or point method. In this method, each answer is compared with already prepared ideal marking scheme (scoring key) and marks are assigned according to the adequacy of the answer.
- ii. The global method, in this method, the examiner first sorts the responses into categories of varying quality base on his general impression on reading the responses.

The motivation behind this study is to seek whether lecturers are equipped with efficient and appropriate test scoring knowledge that will enable them evaluate students fairly and effectively.

However, the consistency of any education system especially tertiary institution relies upon the quality and competence of lecturers, hence this. become the most important factor in tertiary institution system. This is because they are the main focus in the learning process and the outcome of learning depends on lecturers. Meanwhile, students learning cannot be complete until they are assessed through test, otherwise known to be the systematic method of gathering data that will be used to judge students' level or degree of performance. Test undergo construction, administration and scoring and the later which is the area of concern requires possession of sufficient and appropriate skills and knowledge in selecting and employing consistent and appropriate scoring strategies. The National Council on Measurement in Education (NCME) has developed standards for Educational Assessment, among the standard is describing the knowledge and skills of selecting and employing appropriate scoring strategies. Meanwhile, knowledge of test scoring among lecturers can vary as a result of many factors; some of which are their field of knowledge, qualification and years of working experience. Others include age, gender, attitude, perception and competence amongst others. However, in this paper, lecturers in tertiary institutions were reviewed by level or years of lecturers' working experience. Due to the fact that, the higher the extent of working experience, the higher the chances of exposure to different scenarios concerning test scoring. Therefore, the study reviewed lecturers' test scoring knowledge by level of working experience to determine their proportion and find out whether the differences that exist in level of working experience can influence test scoring.

However, from personal experience, tertiary institution lecturers in Zamfara State seem to have insufficient test scoring knowledge; they rather score students' test script without adopting any scoring technique and developing marking scheme. They also feel reluctant in going through any requisite procedure of test scoring. Past researches have shown lack of adequate knowledge base regarding the test scoring strategies; limited training in assessment and failure to employ and adhere to measurement guidelines learned in pre-service/in-service measurement courses. Perhaps, insufficient test scoring knowledge affects tertiary institution assessment process by hindering determining students learning outcome and this will go a long way to establish students' mistrust and unacceptability of scores from lecturers. Similarly, it affects Cumulative Grade Points Average (CGPA) earned by students after graduation, that is error score which

may be higher or lower than the true score. This can have serious implication as qualified applicant is ruled out of being accepted for a job and as such lead to incorrect job placement for applicant who lacks the required skills. Hence, this research determines proportion of lecturers with high, moderate and low test scoring knowledge and also investigates test scoring knowledge differences (if any) on lecturers' field of knowledge.

The result of the study makes an input in the present state of tests scoring knowledge in tertiary institutions of Nigeria. It helps tertiary institutions determine the existence or otherwise of inadequate scoring knowledge among their lecturers and need for in-service training on assessment practice. Also, the result of this study encourages tertiary institutions to enforce rigorous use of assessment skills through ensuring that lecturers have the necessary knowledge, skills and attitudes on marking/scoring tests which is important in improving assessment practice. The outcome of this study provides additional knowledge of establishing valid, reliable and accurate test scores which goes a long way to establish students' trust and acceptability of scores from lecturers. The result of this study probably convinces students, parents and the general public that the cumulative grade points awarded to students (CGPA) can be valid. The study also adds to the body of knowledge on scoring/marking at school level and how lecturers should mark or score tests.

The study was conducted in Zamfara State of Nigeria, and the scope covers all lecturers of university, colleges of education and polytechnics in the state with different qualifications and fields of knowledge, as well as years of working experience. Furthermore, the study focuses on investigating lecturers' test scoring knowledge proportion. Theoretically, Classical Test Theory (CTT) was used for the study, due to its relevance to test scoring.

The study excluded variables like age, teaching subject and gender. Similarly, the study also excluded Monotechnics lecturers (such as College of Health Technology Tsafe, School of Nursing and Midwifery Gusau, College of Agricultural Science Bakura, and so on) in Zamfara State, it also excluded lecturers of Distance Learning institutions such as National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN), National Teachers Institution (NTI) as well as Lecturers of Private tertiary institutions in Zamfara State. Item Response Theory (IRT) was also excluded from the study.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to determine:

- i. The proportion of low experienced, quite experienced, averagely, experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low test scoring knowledge in Zamfara State.

- ii. The test scoring knowledge difference among low experienced, quite experienced, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers in Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The study answered this research question.

1. What is the proportion of low experienced, quite experienced, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low test scoring knowledge in Zamfara State?

Research Hypothesis

The study formulated and tested the hypothesis below at 0.05 level of significance.

- There is no significant difference in the mean score of test scoring knowledge among low experienced, quite experienced, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low test scoring knowledge in Zamfara State.

Methodology

The survey design was used for the study. This is because a survey design is a procedure in quantitative research that gathers data from a sample of population to represent an entire population at a particular point in time with the intention of describing the nature of existing condition or identifying standard condition that can be compared (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007). Therefore, it enables the researcher gather descriptive data from sample of lecturers to enable generalization on the entire lecturers in the study area about their test scoring knowledge. A survey design also enables the researcher find out whether test scoring knowledge differences exist among lectures based on field of knowledge.

The population of the study comprises all lecturers in Zamfara State. According to Zamfara State Directorate for Higher Education (2020), they were one thousand nine hundred and eighteen (1918) lecturers (comprising of 1542 males and 376 females) from tertiary institutions in Zamfara State. This shows that about 80% of the lecturers were males, while 20% were females. The lecturers in universities were six hundred and three (603 [32%]), colleges of education, five hundred and ninety seven (597 [31%]) and polytechnics, seven hundred and eighteen (718 [37%]). The lecturers are of different fields of knowledge (i.e. Education, Engineering, Humanities, Sciences, Social and Management Sciences). A sample size of 300 was used for this study based on the recommendation of Research Advisors (2006) table for determination of sample size. In drawing sample size, multi-stages cluster sampling technique was used in this study. This is because multi-stage sampling entails two or more stages of random sampling based on hierarchical structure of natural clusters within the population (Sedgwick, 2015).

‘Teachers Test Scoring Scale (TTSS)’ was adapted as an instrument of data collection. TTSS was subjected to Content Validity Index (CVI) by administering it to a panel of ten (10) experts for determining the degree of item relevance using four scales of relevance index which revealed average proportion of relevance across all items (S-CVI/Ave) as .95 and average of universal agreement across all items (S-CVI/UA) as .88, and thus considered valid. Similarly, TTSS was pilot tested to thirty (30) lecturers in Zamfara State. The internal consistency reliability test-retest reliability was used and coefficient of .86 was obtained using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Hence, this is considered relative strong and highly reliable in assessing lecturers test scoring knowledge.

The data for this study was analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 25). The research question was answered using descriptive statistics in the form of frequency count and simple percentages. One hypothesis was tested using inferential statistics in the form of ANOVA. According to Cohen, Manion & Morrison, (2007), ANOVA is premised on the same assumption as t-test, that is random sampling, normal distribution of scores, homogeneity of variance, parametric data and it can be used with three or more groups.

Results of the Finding

Answer to Research Question

The research question raised in chapter one was answered below using data organization.

Research Question 1: What is the proportion of low experienced, quite experienced, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low test scoring knowledge in Zamfara State?

Table 1 Proportion of low experienced, quite experienced, average experienced and highly experienced lecturers’ with High, Average and Low Test Scoring Knowledge in Zamfara State.

	Low		Average		High		Total
	Knowledge		Knowledge		Knowledge		
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	
Low Experienced	10	27	62	33	21	34	93
Quite Experienced	13	35	60	31	15	24	88

Average	05	14	35	19	07	11	47
Experienced							
Highly	09	24	33	17	19	31	61
Experienced							
Total	37		190		62		289

Table 1 shows that 27%, 33% and 34% of lecturers with low experience have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring respectively. It also revealed that 35%, 31% and 24% of quite experienced lecturers have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring knowledge. The table also revealed that 14%, 19% and 11% of averagely experienced lecturers have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring. Lastly, 24%, 17% and 31% of highly experienced lecturers have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring knowledge.

Hypotheses Testing

One hypothesis was raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **Hypothesis 1:** There is no significant difference in the mean score of test scoring knowledge among low experienced, quite experienced, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low test scoring knowledge in Zamfara State.

Table 2 Descriptive Statistics on Lecturers’ Test Scoring Knowledge by levels of Working Experience in Zamfara State.

Level of Working Experience	Mean	N	S.D	Std. Error
Low Experienced	16.35	93	2.903	.30431
Quite Experienced	16.00	88	2.881	.30709
Average Experienced	16.19	47	2.726	.39349
Highly Experienced	16.50	61	3.082	.39144

Table 2 above shows the mean scores of lecturers' test scoring knowledge based on years of working experience. From the mean scores, lecturers with high working experience had the highest mean scores of 16.50, followed by lecturers with low working experience with a mean score of 16.35, then quite working experience with 16.19 mean score and at the bottom end were lecturers with average working experience with 16.00 mean score.

Table 3 Analysis of Variance of Lecturers' Test Scoring Knowledge by levels of Working Experience in Zamfara State.

Test-Scoring Knowledge	Sum of Square	Df	F-cal	Sig.
Between Groups	24.718	15	1.325	.186
Within Groups	339.580	273		
Total	364.298	288		

Table 3 shows the analysis of variance of lecturers' test scoring knowledge by years of working experience. From the table, the p-value of .186 is greater than α level of 0.05 level of significance with degree of freedom 15. Thus, the null hypothesis, which stated that there is no significant difference in lecturers' knowledge of test scoring by years of working experience, is therefore accepted. Meanwhile, no significant difference was observed in lecturers' knowledge of test scoring among lecturers' of different years of working experience.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the study revealed that 35%, 31% and 24% of quite experienced lecturers have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring. It also revealed that 14%, 19% and 11% of averagely experience lecturers have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring. Lastly, 24%, 17% and 31% of highly experienced lecturers have low, average and high knowledge of test scoring knowledge. The variation in scores used to determine the proportion of lecturers with high, average and low knowledge of test scoring may be due to lecturers' attitude, competence, perception or ability, and may also occur due to numerous

factors such as guessing or fatigue. It also revealed that lecturers in Zamfara state do not significantly differ in knowledge of test scoring by level of working experience.

The findings of this study is in compliance with theoretical assumptions of classical test theory (CTT) which reflected that each person has true score or error score on the trait being measured, be it a body of knowledge or competence in a skill. Similarly, Abdulrashid,. (2012), McMorrish, & Boothnoyd, (2013), Sani, (2014), and Bello, (2018), corroborated this study, as they revealed that teachers are knowledgeable of test scoring and there is no significant difference among respondents in test scoring knowledge by years/level of working experience.

Finally, the result of this study revealed no significant difference in lecturers' test scoring knowledge among lower experienced, quite experienced, averagely experienced and highly experienced lecturers with high, average and low test scoring knowledge in Zamfara State. This can be ascribed to the fact that the instrument of data collected (i.e. TTSS) administered to lecturers was not completed instantly. They filled the TTSS at interval of days and weeks which is considered as the major factor that affected the data collected, result and conclusion of the study. Therefore, future researchers on this area are recommended to take note of this problem and try to minimize this problem in order to prevent its influence on data collected, result of the study and conclusion.

Conclusions

Despite the personal experience which seems that tertiary institution lecturers in Zamfara State have insufficient test scoring knowledge. From the findings of this study, it can be concluded that tertiary institution lecturers in Zamfara State are knowledgeable on test scoring, and their knowledge of test scoring relatively remains high across all levels of working experience. It can also be concluded that lecturers' test scoring knowledge did not differ significantly by level of working experience. This means lecturers' test scoring knowledge was not affected by field of knowledge.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommends the following:

- Tertiary institutions, Ministry of education and high profile educational stake holders should ensure that lecturers are trained on essential concepts, principles, techniques and procedures of test scoring through in-service training and workshop.
- Tertiary institutions should have a policy on examination/test scoring such as preparing marking scheme when developing a test. The marking scheme should be moderated by the Head of Department.
- Tertiary institutions' administration should monitor the whole assessment process from test construction and administration to test scoring and reporting.

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